

APECS NORDIC PROJECT 2013-2015

Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples
in Nordic Regions

Photo by S.Konyaev

Final Report 2015

Authors: Sharp, L., Paquin, K., Fugmann G. and the APECS Nordic Project Team

Acknowledgements

The APECS Nordic Project Team included 11 members each tasked with specific elements of the project:

- Dr. Gerlis Fugmann (Association of Polar Early Career Scientists / UiT The Arctic University of Norway) Project Manager
- Laura Sharp (Smithsonian Institution, USA,) Project Coordinator
- Laura Lukes (George Mason University, USA) Workshop Organizing Committee
- Sandra Juutilainen (University of Oulu, Finland) Workshop Organizing Committee
- Julie Renee Bull (Toronto Aboriginal Support Services Council) Workshop Organizing Committee
- Yulia Zaika (Faculty of Geography, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia) Webinars Coordinator
- Jocelyn Torma (University of Waterloo, Canada) Webinars Coordinator
- Julia Skupchenko (Syktyvkar State University, Russia) - Database Coordinator
- Mathilde Mansoz, (Lund University, Sweden) Survey Organizing Committee
- Ylva Sjöberg (Stockholm University, Sweden) Survey Organizing Committee
- Sarah Nuernberger (International Development Enterprises, USA) Survey Organizing Committee

Additional ideas and support were provided by Dr. Alexey Pavlov, (Norwegian Polar Institute) and Karolina Paquin (UiT The Arctic University of Norway), as well as Dr. Russell Fielding and Amanda O'Connor of the University of Denver. Without this team the APECS Nordic Project would have been impossible-thanks to the team for their energy, expertise and diligence throughout the project. Ongoing support was also provided by the APECS Executive Committee and Council.

Acknowledgement of funding and support

APECS Nordic's Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Regions project was made possible through the generous support from the **Nordic Council of Ministers' Arctic Cooperation Programme**.

The project was also made possible through the cooperation and funding support for the APECS International Directorate by the **Research Council of Norway, UiT – The Arctic University of Norway** and the **Norwegian Polar Institute**.

Additional financial support for the 2-day Workshop in Helsinki, Finland was provided by the **US National Science Foundation (NSF)**, **International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)**, and the **Swedish Polar Research Secretariat**.

The 2-day workshop, attached to the Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) 2014 would not have been possible without the sixty international early career researchers (both indigenous and non-indigenous), community members and mentors who traveled to Helsinki to offer their insights, expertise, experiences and observations into this project. Thank you for all your contributions and interest in this project. A special thank you also to IASC and the Local Organization Committee of the ASSW 2014 for their cooperation in the planning of the workshop, providing free early bird registration to ASSW for our workshop participants and for organizing a joint icebreaker event. Additionally, we extended our thanks to APECS Finland who were welcoming hosts organizing local cultural activities for workshop and ASSW participants.

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Executive Summary

Indigenous populations in the Nordic regions are one of the key players in current and future research of the Arctic, as their traditional knowledge is critical to understanding the impacts of climate change in the region. The APECS community understands the importance of bringing indigenous and non-indigenous early career researchers and northern communities together to create a synergy with the overall long-term goal to be better prepared for and adapt to the rapidly changing Arctic environment and building better research relationships.

For this reason, the APECS Nordic Project “Bridging Polar Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries” started in summer 2013, funded by the Nordic Council of Ministers. It aimed to meet the demand for stronger, more efficient communication and engagement between ECRs, northern communities and holders of traditional knowledge in the Nordic region. The project used several ways and tools to achieve this:

- enhance cooperation between Arctic indigenous and non-indigenous ECRs from the Nordic countries with communities and local traditional knowledge holders by providing platforms and communication tools for the already established APECS national branches in Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark and Russia (see Chapter 2.1.)
- provide relevant training through a series of online webinars and an in-person workshop (see Chapter 2.2);
- identify stakeholders and current policies as well as challenges and best practices in collaboration between indigenous and non-indigenous ECRs and northern communities in Nordic countries (including incorporation of Traditional Knowledge into research practices) (see chapter 2.3).
- help develop a set of resources on how to work with Indigenous peoples and Indigenous communities for ECRs as well as indigenous youths (see Chapter 2.5.)

The project and this report identified the following recommendations for future research:

- Researchers and educational institutions should assume greater responsibility to become informed and knowledgeable about community history, norms, expectations and concerns prior to field work
- Educational Institutions should provide/create policy ensuring training of local research participants to ensure mutual benefits
- Indigenous community members should become research partners and ensure local indigenous knowledge integration in the research project/plan from the outset.
- Researchers and community members should be mindful of different worldviews or epistemologies through all phases of research project.

- Research funding institutions should account for a long field season, return visits, compensation for local indigenous research partners, interview informants, costs of translations, interpreters as well as dissemination of results in all Nordic research.
- Strive for research sustainability or longevity of research initiatives to promote synthesis of research projects and results.

1. About the APECS Nordic Project

Establishing authentic collaborations and strengthening communication between indigenous community members and researchers is crucial for current and future research across the Arctic. In many Nordic countries, calls for measures and mechanisms that provide guidance for indigenous-researcher relationships have recently seen greater interest and attention (Stordahl et al. 2015; Lukes et al, 2014; Keskitalo et al. 2011). The social sciences in particular have acknowledged the inclusion of local traditional knowledge as critical to understanding and responding to these rapid changes (Krupnik and Jolly, 2002; Pulsifer et al. 2012; Pearce et al. 2009; Eide et al., 2014; Usher, 2000; Berkes 1993). Across the Arctic, scientists have been increasingly recognizing the value of working with indigenous community members (Huntington, 2000; Armitage et al. 2011; Berkes, 1993). Similarly, indigenous communities are increasingly taking greater ownership over and playing a more active role in the rapid influx of research projects and researcher presence in their communities (ITK and NRI, 2007). Although these changes occur arctic-wide, many of the most well known examples of successful collaboration have emerged from the Canadian Arctic and Alaska (e.g. Gearheard and Shirley, 2007; Gearheard et al. 2006; Krupnik et al. 2010; Pearce et al. 2009). These examples illustrate collaborations in which communities were central to the projects as research partners, where local and traditional indigenous knowledge was fully incorporated into the research results, and where communities were included in the outcomes of the research as co-authors and conference presenters.

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)

APECS started in 2006 as an initiative of the IPY 2007-2008, and has been identified by the major IPY sponsors, the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the International Council for Science (ICSU), as one of the most important legacies from the IPY efforts. Comprising more than 5000 members hailing from 76 countries worldwide and corresponding to every major and minor polar research division and discipline, APECS represents the remarkable diversity that is shaping the future of polar research. APECS works closely with many international organizations (<http://www.apecs.is/about-apecs/partners-and-sponsors>) and leading polar researchers, educators and funding agencies to provide a continuum of knowledge in the field of polar research for generations to come. APECS stimulates interdisciplinary and international research collaborations and develops effective future leaders in polar research, education and outreach. We achieve these goals by:

- Facilitating international and interdisciplinary networking to share ideas and experiences and to develop new research directions and collaborations;
- Providing opportunities for professional career development; and
- Promoting education and outreach as an integral component of polar research and to stimulate future generations of polar researchers.

Rationale for the APECS Nordic Project

In the wake of the IPY 2007-2008, and in an era of rapid technological advancements where communication with even the more remote regions of our planet has become easier, the APECS community understands the importance of bringing ECRs, Indigenous peoples and youth together. APECS recognizes the need for this synergy, with the overall long-term goal to be better prepared for and adapt to the rapidly changing Arctic environment. Its network includes both indigenous and non-indigenous early career researchers working with Northern communities and within the traditional areas of Indigenous Peoples in the Nordic countries, Northern Canada, Greenland, and the Russian Arctic. Therefore, APECS brings together a unique source of expertise on the issue. As a grass-roots initiative, APECS has done several initiatives and projects to foster interest in Arctic ECRs to be engaged in community-driven research and in work that involves traditional knowledge (e.g. Tondu et al. 2014).

For this reason, the APECS Nordic Project “Bridging Polar Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries” started in summer 2013, funded by the Nordic Council of Ministers (Norden). It focused on enhancing the engagement between early career researchers (ECRs) and Indigenous peoples members in several ways:

- the project aimed to enhance cooperation between Arctic indigenous and non-indigenous ECRs from the Nordic countries with communities and local traditional knowledge holders (see Chapter 2.1.)
- it provided relevant training through a series of online webinars and an in person workshop (see Chapter 2.2);
- It identified current challenges in collaboration between indigenous and non-indigenous ECRs in Nordic countries, including incorporation of Traditional Knowledge into research practices (see Chapter 2.3);
- it helped develop a set of resources on how to work with Indigenous peoples and Indigenous communities for ECRs as well as indigenous youths (see Chapter 2.5.)

Terminology

To provide a clear understanding of the scope of this project and report, it is necessary to define and contextualize the use of various terms herein.

- **‘Early Career Researchers’**: In the context of this project, this term refers generally to undergraduate and graduate students, PhD students and postdoctoral researchers, early faculty members and other early career professionals, individuals and leaders conducting research.
- **‘Nordic Region’**: In the context of this project refers to a specific geographical region and people. It is defined by the Nordic Council of Ministers as the following: “The Nordic Region

consists of Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Finland and Iceland, as well as the Faroe Islands, Greenland, and Åland” (Nordic Council of Ministers, 2015). For the purpose of this report, the Sami regions of the Kola Peninsula of the Russia Northwest have also been included.

Figure 1: Nordic Region. Source: Nordregio, 2014 (Map design: Linus Rispling, Nordregio).

- For simplification, **‘Indigenous’** peoples in Nordic regions are mainly discussed throughout the report, however, it is widely understood that many non-indigenous people reside in Nordic regions and are not intended to be excluded. Furthermore, this project refers to the Sami people broadly, but recognizes that there are multiple and different Sami territories across the north. Similarly, the use of the term indigenous in this report extends to numerous regions across Russia including the territories of the roughly forty distinct indigenous peoples across the Russian north and Siberia (Arctic Council 2015).
- **Traditional knowledge:** This project uses the Arctic Council definition of traditional knowledge. It describes it as follows: “a systematic way of thinking and knowing that is elaborated and applied to phenomena across biological, physical, cultural and linguistic systems. Traditional Knowledge is owned by the holders of that knowledge, often collectively, and is uniquely

expressed and transmitted through indigenous languages. It is a body of knowledge generated through cultural practices, lived experiences including extensive and multigenerational observations, lessons and skills. It has been developed and verified over millennia and is still developing in a living process, including knowledge acquired today and in the future, and it is passed on from generation to generation.” (Arctic Council, 2015).

2. APECS Nordic Project Results

The APECS Nordic Project results are discussed in the following five sections:

- **Enhancing cooperation** between Arctic (non-) indigenous ECRs from the Nordic countries with young Indigenous Peoples (mainly high school students and young adults) and Local Traditional Knowledge holders (chapter 2.1.);
- Providing relevant **training** through a series of online webinars and an in-person workshop (chapter 2.2.);
- **Identifying current challenges** in collaboration between (non-) indigenous ECRs and Indigenous youths in Nordic countries, including incorporation of Traditional Knowledge into research practices (chapter 2.3.);
- Producing relevant and up-to-date **communication materials** and **tools** in English and in the Nordic languages (chapter 2.4);
- Developing **a set of resources** on how to work with Indigenous peoples and Indigenous communities for ECRs as well as indigenous youths (chapter 2.5)

2.1. Enhancing Cooperation

Indigenous and non-indigenous early career researchers in Nordic regions and communities share a range of common interests and concerns (see results section 2.2). Despite these common interests, there exist few Nordic-wide research initiatives, organizations or collaborations that specifically foster cooperation and collaboration amongst indigenous and non-indigenous ECRs, Northern communities and elder traditional knowledge holders. **Enhancing cooperation** was achieved through several initiatives:

Strengthening of the APECS Nordic Network

APECS has national committees in Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark and Russia. More synergies between them to strengthen these committees and to foster exchange between them was one of the goals of this project. Allowing Nordic researchers to establish networks both within the scientific community and with Indigenous peoples at an early stage in their career will help future collaborations in polar research and will facilitate addressing complex challenges posed by the climate change in the region. Practical steps of development of the Nordic network included:

- Creation of a dedicated project website section (<http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-project-2013-2015>)

- Meeting of representatives of the APECS Nordic National Committees during the APECS World Summit 2015 (6 – 8 June 2015, Sofia, Bulgaria) to discuss further collaboration within the region and possible future joint activities.
- Promotion of APECS Nordic project and networks in the APECS social media channels; presentation of the project and network at several scientific conferences; generate attention from and interest for the general public as well as attract new ECRs willing to work with Indigenous peoples and Northern communities.

APECS Nordic Database

The APECS Nordic project created an open, online Nordic focused database to connect researchers, project leaders, community members, leaders and organizations with an interest in the Nordic region (<http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-database>). This database, launched in November 2013, was a fundamental starting point for building cooperation, collaboration and networking amongst ECRs and indigenous communities in Nordic regions. The database featured an open source, public table of contact information for the Nordic researcher community. Individuals, or organizations were encouraged to provide information about themselves, their research interest and expertise, current research position, the reason for joining the network, as well as the region / community their research is focused on. Others interested in collaborating on research projects or simply learning more about a particular region are encouraged to contact them. The database will remain on the website indefinitely to allow for future researchers, community members and project leaders to continue to facilitate networking opportunities and cooperation amongst Nordic ECRs and community members.

Other initiatives to foster cooperation

In addition, a six-part webinar series was organized (discussed in section 2.2.). The webinars were online, open and accessible to anyone with access to the Internet. They focused on a range of Nordic research relevant topics such as “Youth indigenous peoples in education and outreach” by Dmitriy Berezhkov, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, which promoted the indigenous youth voice and providing guidance for outreach planners in polar communities. Furthermore, the APECS Nordic project has presented several APECS Nordic posters at major international polar conferences to promote the overall project, but more specifically to inform Nordic audiences of the forums discussed in this report now available to Nordic researchers and community members, indigenous and non-indigenous. Additionally, the APECS Nordic project has produced and will continue to publish journal articles (e.g. Bull and Juutilainen 2014, Lukes et al. 2014) in leading polar and other relevant scientific journals about the project results.

2.2. Training

Providing relevant **training** through a series of online webinars and an in-person workshop was another major outcome of the project.

Webinar Series

APECS built on previous experience in the field of online presentation and seminars by conducting a webinar series for the APECS Nordic Project, bringing a new focus on the synergy between Northern Indigenous and non-indigenous polar ECRs. Already since 2010, the APECS Virtual Poster Sessions (VPS, <http://tinyurl.com/apecs-vps-2010-2012>) was a successful project funded by the NCM in 2009-2010 under the previous Nordic Council of Ministers' Arctic Co-operation programme (Renner et al. 2011, Pavlov et al. 2012). It created a web infrastructure for sharing research posters as well as presenting and discussing results online outside the four walls of the conference. Building on the success of this project, APECS has conducted several webinar series since 2010, both on research and career development topics. For the APECS Nordic project a series of 6 webinars has been conducted from October till December 2013.

The webinar series held in the GoToWebinar system, identified current research challenges from the perspective of ECRs and Indigenous peoples and aimed to define potential solutions to overcome these existing challenges to communication and other research issues. Speakers include leading experts, early career researchers, Indigenous youth and Indigenous researchers from Nordic regions as well as others. The webinars were recorded and the recordings are all available together with a short description about each topic and the speaker information online on the APECS website <http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-webinars-2013>.

➤ **Bridging the Gap: Indigenous, Social and Natural Science Perspectives on Research Relationships in Nordic Countries**

Gail Fondahl (IASSA President, University of Northern British Columbia, Canada) and **Gunhild Ninis Rosqvist** (Stockholm University and Tarfala Research Station, Sweden)

Abstract: Every story has at least two sides. The story of climate change research in Nordic communities has three. This webinar was intended to highlight the main communication challenges faced by natural scientists, as well as social scientists, in their community-based research efforts. As well, it sought to highlight Indigenous perspectives on how to open a successful dialogue and begin to overcome challenges. In this webinar, the audience was introduced to the fundamental issues that can hinder cross-communication between social scientists, natural scientists and members of indigenous communities in Nordic regions. When communication is compromised, relevant knowledge and evidence from indigenous sources can be left out of scientific considerations, and the validity of findings can be compromised in turn. Climate change is a

problem that impacts us all, so it is essential to start working together to find solutions we can share.

➤ **Youth indigenous peoples in education and outreach**

Dmitriy Berezchkov (UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norway)

Abstract: Engaging Indigenous youth in research that guides the development of their home communities is not a matter of simply giving them tools to think scientifically. Part of the purpose of education and outreach is to create a platform for different kinds of knowledge to merge, and to cultivate innovative solutions for a shared future. This webinar sought to promote the indigenous youth voice and provide guidance for outreach planners in polar communities.

➤ **Indigenous Knowledge management through Information and Communication Technologies**

Heidi McCann, Colleen Strawhacker, Peter Pulsifer (Exchange for Local Observations and Knowledge of the Arctic (ELOKA) at the National Snow and Ice Data Centre, USA)

Abstract: Community-based research by, with, and for Arctic Indigenous peoples has become recognized as a valuable source of data and often involves knowledge and observations of residents and local experts. These data frequently take the form of recordings or books, but recent development of Information Technologies of various kinds such as GIS, interactive mapping, and websites documenting oral histories allow for Indigenous Arctic research to be made available to communities, researchers, and other interested groups. In this webinar, the speakers presented a review of various systems being developed through the Exchange for Local Observations and Knowledge in the Arctic (ELOKA) as well as discussed the opportunities to collect, manage and represent Indigenous knowledge through Information and Communication Technology. Throughout the presentation, the speakers discussed issues that must be considered and addressed throughout the project including practical challenges, appropriate representation, and ethical and legal issues.

➤ **Reflections on Sami research: being a researcher and being researched.**

Else Grete Broderstad (Center for Sami Studies at the UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norway)

Abstract: What does it mean to be a researcher, but also to be researched at the same time? In this webinar the presenter shared Sami perspectives and thoughts on this very cutting-edge of community-based research.

➤ **Getting in touch with Nordic communities: Reaching out gently**

Svetlana Usenyuk (Aalto University School of Art, Design and Architecture, Helsinki, Finland) and **Heidi McCann, Colleen Strawhacker** and **Peter Pulsifer** (Exchange for Local Observations and Knowledge of the Arctic at the National Snow and Ice Data Centre, USA)

Abstract: Approaching an unfamiliar community can be a challenge for a researcher, considering it takes time for a community to come to know and trust a new face. The process of building a trusting relationship between a community and a research group is delicate, and we must all tread lightly towards co-operative cohabitation during research efforts. This webinar intended to highlight some difficulties faced by researchers and community members, even of a shared background, in introducing the prospect of collaborating in a shared space.

➤ **Essential keys to successful research summarized: Building collegial relationships with Indigenous community members,**

Jocelyn Torma (University of Waterloo, Canada) and **Yulia Zaika** (Faculty of Geography, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia)

Abstract: The sixth and final webinar in this series summarized the key points made by the speakers featured in the previous five, and illuminated some practical takeaways that will be useful to researchers and indigenous community members alike. The insights shared in this series ranged from tips about initial contact to nurture lasting relationships after data collection needs have been met. The main relevant theme is cultural inclusion, in a day-to-day sense, in gathering and disseminating knowledge through formal and informal avenues, and in recording and databasing a complete set of observations that can be interpreted and critiqued from many perspectives. This summary offered an overview of essential considerations that will enhance the field research experience for everyone involved and optimize the value of scientific conclusions by generally guiding the most well-informed analyses of data.

APECS Nordic Workshop “Connecting early career researchers and community-driven research in the North”, Helsinki, Finland, 7 – 8 April 2014

The 2-day APECS Nordic workshop “Connecting early career researchers and community driven research in the North” was one of the central activities of the APECS Nordic Project (<http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-workshop-2014>). The workshop was organized in conjunction with the Arctic Science Summit Week 2014 (ASSW - <http://www.assw2014.fi/>) and the Arctic Observing Summit 2014 in Helsinki from 7- 8 April 2014. In total, the workshop welcomed more than 50 participants, including mentors and experts and as well as indigenous and non-indigenous ECRs (<http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-workshop-article>). With a major focus on early career participants from the Nordic region, the in-person event explored the need for integration amongst Indigenous people, researchers with researchers.

Over the course of two days, participants engaged with timely, thought-provoking presentations by **Gail Fondahl** (UNBC, Canada), **Heidi Eriksen** (Utsjoki Health Center), **Anna Afanasyeva** (International Barents Secretariat), **Arja Rautio** (Thule Institute) and **Roberto Delgado** (USC/NSF), and offered

valuable, insights during themed breakout sessions. Sessions topics including existing research policies, stakeholder interests, communication and successful collaboration led to honest, and challenging discussions about the real challenges and concerns that indigenous researchers and non-indigenous researchers face when conducting research in the Arctic. While most agreed, for example, that successful collaborations needed to involve community members in the research process, this was not always taking place. One concern that was raised during the workshop was the scarce representation of Nordic indigenous people in the workshop itself. While every effort was made to advertise the workshop to all possible outlets, there was a higher representation of early career researchers in attendance. This and many other related questions were raised and thoroughly considered over the two days.

The framework of the workshop included plenary sessions, breakout sessions, panel discussions, group works to develop materials on future interactions between researchers and Indigenous peoples. Discussions focused on stakeholders, policies for working with indigenous groups, successful collaboration models, building a community as well as broader impacts including communicating results and outreach. Initial results from the workshop have been published (Bull and Juutilainen 2014; Lukes et al. 2014) and the discussions contributed to the findings presented in this report.

Figure 2: APECS Nordic Workshop Participants, April 8 2014.

2.3. Current Collaboration Challenges

In order to gain an understanding of how to improve cooperation, collaboration and engagement between ECRs and Nordic Indigenous community members (researchers and non-researchers), the APECS Nordic project sought to define several key elements. In addition to the discussions during the workshop and the webinar series, a survey was one of the methods to determine these.

Several survey campaigns among Northern Indigenous Peoples have been implemented in recent years (e.g. Kruse et al. 2009). Many of them focused on health, environment, urbanization, etc. However, little attention was paid to specific questions of interactions between ECRs, Indigenous peoples and Northern communities, western science and Traditional Knowledge, and how both could interact in more efficient and sustainable ways. At the same time, the importance of appropriate education and training (for ECRs) required when interacting with Indigenous peoples has only recently become widely recognized, largely due to increased research (and industrial) activity in the Arctic.

APECS has both indigenous and non-indigenous members. Knowing both realms, especially indigenous early career researchers can provide an extremely valuable source of information and knowledge. Several were therefore invited as early/mid-career mentors to all activities of this project and also to take part in the surveys. APECS has gained extensive experience in designing and conducting surveys during and after the IPY 2007-2008. One of the most explicit examples being an education and outreach survey and assessment which resulted in the publication of the Education and Outreach Catalogue (Provencher et al., 2011) or the currently ongoing joint APECS – Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) Project Survey “Where are they now” <http://www.apecs.is/research/apecs-projects/apecs-clic-where-are-they-now.html>.

In the APECS Nordic project, the survey addressed Indigenous communities and polar ECRs interested in or working with them <http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-survey-2014>. A mixed-model of open-ended and multiple-choice questions was used in the assessment. Apart from the English original survey version, the survey was translated into Northern Sami, Swedish, and Finnish. Ethics approvals were sought in each of the applicable countries. See the Survey Draft in appendix 5.3.

The survey was sent out in early February 2014 and was open until the summer of 2014. It was made available on the APECS website, and was delivered through our partners to Northern communities using targeted listservs and Northern community contacts. Participants of the APECS Nordic Workshop were also encouraged to fill out the survey. In total 114, the survey received 114 responses. Only 86 of those were used for the analysis as the rest were either incomplete or were not from people living or researching in the Arctic. Methods for analysis of collected data included descriptive statistics as well as content analysis. Results helped to assess the current state of the communication between scientists and Indigenous people, and suggested ways for improvement. A plain language summary will be developed until the end of 2015, and will be translated into the as many of the Nordic languages as

possible and distributed to all partner organizations. Survey participants also had the option of including their email for inclusion in the dissemination of the results as well.

The survey, workshop discussions and webinars provided answers to several key questions:

1. Who are the stakeholders?
2. What are the policies and processes that are currently in place?
3. What are the current challenges that exist amongst these stakeholders?
4. What are the existing programs that are examples of best practices?
5. What is needed to improve collaboration and engagement?

Stakeholders

This project identified that stakeholders in the context of early career researchers and Indigenous peoples in Nordic regions expand beyond those two key stakeholder groups. In fact, there are many more players involved in influencing the research climate in Nordic countries. During the workshop discussions, participants identified more than 30 different entities that can be grouped into 17 different types listed in figure 3. It is important to note here that both ECRs and indigenous participants identified the stakeholders listed here.

Figure 3: Major stakeholders identified in APECS Nordic Project.

Current Policies

The APECS Nordic project set out to identify policies and protocols for working with and in indigenous communities currently in place in Nordic regions. While the responses from the workshop and survey varied from country to country, there was no universal policy in place for the entire Nordic region. Workshop participants identified a range of policies, protocols, research ethical guidelines, conventions and practices that exist at various levels including national and local governments, universities and NGOs (see chapter 2.5). However, these policies were not consistent across the Nordic region or across research areas and were also not necessarily implemented. For example, the current status in Finland was described by one workshop participant, as having “numerous research-ethical legislation and guidelines but not followed when working with Sami communities”.

Other Arctic regions have developed different policies. In Canada, for example, the Inuit *Nunangat* or Inuit homelands, Nunavut, Nunatsiavut, Inuvialuit and Nunavik, are represented by a single organization, the Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami (ITK). The ITK has at least one appointed Research Advisor for each of the four regions. Each Research Advisor acts as a gatekeeper to those interested in studying in the respective regions by reviewing research proposals for projects of any kind. Research Advisors employ evaluation criteria similar to the guidelines outlined in the 2007 publication “Negotiating Research Relationships with Inuit Communities, a Guide for Researchers” (ITK and NRI 2007). This is arguably one of the earliest publications that promotes an indigenous-led framework for researchers conducting work with Inuit, in Inuit communities. The outcome of this policy for researchers is the definition of a common set of standards and expectations of research initiatives taking place within any of the Inuit *Nunangat* homelands. While these are prominent in the Canadian Arctic, such a set of common standards does not currently exist for indigenous peoples in Nordic regions.

Further, others suggested that while policies may exist, implementation is a challenge. Although some participants suggested that there is “no standard policy-national, international, local... each person has to invent/develop their own method...” several cited the UN Declaration of the Rights of Indigenous Peoples as one universal policy applicable to all nations, including those of the Nordic region. It was clearly stated by one indigenous participant that there is no stronger tool than the UN Declaration for working with indigenous communities. Others suggested that it may be preferred to not implement policies that researcher and communities are bound to, as it “might be easier to work with indigenous people without a set of policies and protocol to follow”. Further, others indicated that the current practice of trial and error is perhaps more appropriate to allow for practices that are “specific to (the) project”. It was highlighted by several participants, that if a policy or set of guidelines for conducting research in Nordic regions is developed, it is critical that indigenous peoples of Nordic region are fundamental to the drafting and shaping of the document/discussion. Further, such a document should be available in the all Nordic languages, including indigenous languages.

Current Challenges

Research in any environment presents unique challenges and obstacles. In the context of the Nordic region when research is undertaken in indigenous communities by non-local, non-indigenous researchers, this presents another layer of complexity. This project determined that challenges and concerns are evident for both parties; the researchers (both indigenous and non-indigenous) and the communities in which the research is taking place.

Results from the project survey revealed some of the most common concerns for both parties. Distance both geographically and culturally between the researchers and the communities in which they conduct research is quite vast. Out of those surveyed, only seven percent had their homes located within 50 kilometers of their research site. On the same note, more than 60 percent of respondents were based over 1000 kilometers of their research site, and furthermore, 42 percent were based over 3000 kilometers away from their research site. This literal distance between the researchers and the locations in which they conduct their research highlights an obvious challenge presented to Nordic researchers, and without doubt, the communities in which the research is taking place. With such distances researchers are likely to be less familiar with local norms, customs, social systems and protocols, leading to inevitable challenges for the researcher, and the community. Analysis from our survey clearly shows that particularly for those respondents living 1000km, 2000km, and 3000km this is true. “We see that researchers who live further away from their research site reported lower levels of understanding of the local culture and customs of their study areas”. For indigenous community members, cultural familiarity, language learning and knowledge of local history and land rights topped the list of local needs and priorities (see figure 4)

A second item highlighted by the survey pertained to local involvement in research projects. As indicated also in figure 4, participation in research, researcher benefits and incorporation of local knowledge are priorities and needs of indigenous communities in research projects. Research collaborations in Nordic regions are increasing and incorporation of local indigenous researchers and knowledge are becoming more common. A total of 44 percent of our survey respondents indicated that they involve local indigenous people in their research. Incorporating local knowledge into research is also becoming more recognized Arctic-wide, as critical to ensure local involvement and validity of results. Local knowledge and traditional knowledge itself is now understood to hold vast accurate and reliable information about the local environment, climate and biology (Huntington, 2000; Krupnik et al. 2010; Pulsifer et al. 2012). The degree to which this information is incorporated into research however, is still a concern (Thornton and Scheer, 2012). This is substantiated by the results from the project survey. Researchers who directly involved indigenous people in their research observed with higher certainty that indigenous people have an understanding of their local environment. For researchers, they are often focused on their research goals and meeting their research requirements within a specific time frame, budget and under certain parameters sometimes prescribed by funding agencies. While researchers are working with local indigenous community members, not all have the knowledge

of how to do so, the connections within the community to establish a relationship or identify neither the potential research collaborators, nor the timeframe to build a relationship or the budget to support a longer field season that can be required.

Figure 4: Indigenous Needs & Expectations

Best Practices

A number of best practices and features of successful collaboration were identified throughout the project. Many of these are practices applicable across a variety of research contexts, however several are specific to the concerns and circumstances of the Nordic region and indigenous communities. The most common thread amongst the practices pertained to mutually beneficial outcomes.

As outlined earlier in the report, researchers have needs and priorities, and likewise indigenous community members have needs and priorities. Understanding these different and potentially common sets of interests at the outset of the research project can facilitate an open, honest dialogue about the purpose of the research and what the potential outcomes and benefits could look like for the researcher and the community. Many examples of successful collaboration identified

“Successful collaboration is...active participation of indigenous peoples in the entire research process – from project design to publication”. – APECS Nordic Workshop Participant, 2014.

in the project were characterized as community-lead, fostering equal partnerships, transparency, trust, long term commitment, sustainability of research results, setting realistic goals, and ensuring appropriate feedback and return of research results to the community.

Best practice examples including specific research projects, researchers/research methods and organizations mentioned included the following:

- Bowhead Whale Tracking Project (Barrow, Alaska).
- Peter Pulsifer, Exchange for Local Observations and Knowledge of the Arctic (ELOKA)
- Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami, National Inuit Organization, Canada
- Ittaq Heritage and Research Centre of Clyde River, Nunavut

Similarly, these projects and examples can be characterized as community-lead, directly involving community researchers, ownership of the research by the community, integration of or reliance on local knowledge holders and sources, and a very long-term research process. Certainly these specific projects are not necessarily relevant to the Nordic context, however the common features of these projects highlight what successful collaborative research might look like between non-indigenous researchers and indigenous communities. Additional features of successful collaboration identified were good rapport with the community (or at least the community leaders and or elders), flexibility built into projects, continuity of research, well planned outreach and follow up with the community, managing expectations.

Needed Improvements

The results from this project outline a series of issues and concerns in Nordic research that could use improvement in order to bridge early career researchers and indigenous community members and researchers. It is possible to outline these around the pre-research phase, the research phase and post-research phase.

a) Pre-Research

Prior to research or fieldwork begins, it is important for researchers to not only complete their obligatory ethics training and research methods courses, but also become informed about the region and community in which they will be conducting their research. This includes taking courses on the history and background of the community and overall region so that the researcher is knowledgeable and informed of the relevant social systems, land use rights, governance systems, and other local interests. Additionally, familiarizing oneself with the local language or languages would demonstrate a sign of respect, and assist in developing a rapport with the community. In order to meet the aim of achieving mutual benefits between researchers and communities, it is useful for the researcher to do some preliminary research about the community's current priorities, needs and goals in terms of research.

Further, to avoid the possibility of ‘research fatigue’ early career researchers should make a concerted effort to make contact with or at the least, research and review the existing resources that have come from research projects already conducted in the community. In addition, making personal contacts in the community either through more senior researchers already known by the community, or by contacting the local community government, research office or other relevant organizations to introduce yourself, your research plan and begin a dialogue about the research goals. This step could begin the process of integrating local knowledge in the project and possibly identifying local research partners or research assistants. Budget preparations should make considerations for a longer research phase, avoiding the problem of ‘fly in, fly out’ research. Budgets should also set aside funds to compensate research assistants or interview informants where appropriate locally.

b) Research Phase

When research begins, information should be made available or circulated to community members. Particularly if a researcher is working in a small community, the presence of the researcher will be obvious and locals deserve to know the reasoning for your presence and your intentions for being in their community. Likewise, researchers should make themselves available to community questions about the project, and be willing to attend local events to get to know the community and to allow them to know the researcher.

Concern was also raised during this project about differing epistemologies or worldviews between non-indigenous researchers and indigenous community members. Researchers in particular would benefit from familiarizing themselves with the literature on the topic of research in the context of both western and indigenous epistemologies. As one workshop participant pointed out, “[there are] different epistemologies of indigenous people (and this doesn’t always mesh well with Western ideologies”.

c) Post-Research

Researcher follow-up and dissemination is an additional area of concern in Nordic regions. Currently, researchers are not required per se, to produce research materials designed specifically for the community. While a standard policy may not be the proper approach, the post-research phase of collaboration should not be overlooked. Research dissemination format is an important point of consideration. Indigenous communities may have a preferred method for learning about the research results. Some examples include an informal presentation at a local community gathering place or local event, a radio station broadcast, through community research partners, through story-telling, films or comics. Finally, and perhaps most obviously, dissemination materials regardless of format, should be made available in the local language(s). The costs of translations included in the research budget and proposal at the outset. Following the same thread as the pre-research phase, researchers should be budgeting for a follow up visit to return research results and ensure an opportunity for local verification of results, confirm that local knowledge is integrated into the research, and that the research accurately represents the community, prior to disseminating the research in scientific journals.

2.4. Communication Materials

The primary host for all communication materials from this project were the project webpages, found through the Research section of the APECS main website (<http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-project-2013-2015>). Through this project, a collection of communication materials has been produced in the form of posters, conference summaries and a website. This main report and subsequent executive summary report aside, there are a series of poster presentations, summary articles and scientific publications that are also referenced on the project webpages. These materials, including this report, are expected to be translated and disseminated through a series of relevant indigenous Nordic networks, organizations, institutions, universities, and researcher communities in late 2015 / early 2016.

2.5. Resources

Listed in this section are examples of relevant external resources collected by the APECS Nordic Project team available through other organizations and projects and describing initiatives beyond the scope of this report. These include sources of best practices, projects, legislation and education with links to access further information. Some are based in or relevant for multiple Nordic countries, while others involve a collaboration that may be applicable Nordic wide. The list published on the APECS Nordic Website is not meant to be exhaustive but is welcoming additions at any time (<http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-resources>):

International

- ILO Convention 169 (<http://www.ilo.org/indigenous/Conventions/no169/lang--en/index.htm>) - ratified in the Nordic region so far only by Norway and Denmark
- The UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous peoples: http://www.un.org/esa/socdev/unpfii/documents/DRIPS_en.pdf - signed by all Nordic countries. Russia has not signed
- UN Convention on Biological Diversity Article 8 (j) [see also The Árbediehtu Project] and 10 (c).
 - Akwé: Kon Guidelines – “voluntary guidelines for the conduct of cultural, environmental and social impact assessment regarding developments proposed to take place on, or which are likely to impact on, sacred sites and on lands and waters traditionally occupied or used by indigenous and local communities” (<https://www.cbd.int/traditional/guidelines.shtml>)
 - The Tkarihwaie:ri code of Ethical Conduct : <https://www.cbd.int/traditional/code.shtml>
- UNESCO's Convention on the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=17716&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html

- UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions
http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=31038&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
- Arctic Council: Ottawa Traditional Knowledge Principles: Traditional Knowledge.
<http://www.arcticpeoples.org/images/2015/ottradknowlprinc.pdf>.

Organisation, Research Institutions / Centres etc.:

- Arctic Council - <http://www.arctic-council.org/>
- The Sami Parliament – Established in Finland (<http://www.samediggi.fi/>), Norway (<http://www.sametinget.no/>), and Sweden (<http://www.sametinget.se/>). :
- Sami Council - <http://www.saamicouncil.net/?deptid=1116>
- International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry - <http://reindeerherding.org/about-us/>
- Association of World Reindeer Herders - <http://reindeerherding.org/wrh/>
- Center for Sami Studies, UiT The Arctic University of Norway : <http://www.sami.uit.no/sdg/senteret/indexen.html>
- International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs – An international non-profit organization representing indigenous peoples around the world, including information on Arctic peoples - <http://www.iwgia.org/regions/arctic>
- Sami University College - <http://samas.no/en>
- Saemien Sijte – sørsamisk museum og kultursenter - <http://saemiensijte.no/>
- Árran Lule Sámi Center - <http://www.rran.no/>
- Sami museum network RiddoDuottarMuseat : http://rdm.no/english/about_rdm/

Relevant publications:

- Community Based Monitoring Handbook – Lessons from the Arctic (CAFF) - (<http://www.caff.is/monitoring-series/9-community-based-monitoring-handbook-lessons-from-the-arctic-and-beyond>)
- Declarations of the World Reindeer Herders Congresses
<http://reindeerherding.org/wrh/declarations/>
- Publications Archive of the International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry
<http://library.arcticportal.org/view/divisions/icr.html>

Relevant projects:

- INTERACT (<http://www.eu-interact.org/outreach2/>)
- The Northern Forum – Bear and Natives in the North Project (<http://www.northernforum.org/index.php/en/projects/environment/bear-and-natives-in-the-north>)
- The Arctic Governance Project <http://arcticgovernance.custompublish.com/home.132703.en.html>
- Ealat project : <http://reindeerherding.org/tag/ealat/>
- The Árbodiehtu Project (2009) : <http://www.arbediehtu.no/index.php/no/>
- CAVIAR Project (Community Adaptation and Vulnerability in the Arctic Regions) : <http://www.ipy.org/images/uploads/CAVIAR.pdf>
- Focalpoint North <http://site.uit.no/focalpoint/>
- Fávllis Network (Norway) <http://site.uit.no/favllis/>
- Finmark landscape <http://site.uit.no/tundra/associated-projects/finmark-landscape/>
- Hunters in transition <http://site.uit.no/hunter/>
- Indigenous People and Multicultural Societies <http://site.uit.no/montana/>
- Indigenous Religion(s). Local Grounds, Global Networks - https://en.uit.no/forskning/forskningsgrupper/gruppe?p_document_id=383890

Other interesting websites

- KIVU Nature TK Resources – a website with links to Best Practices, Traditional Knowledge Centres, Traditional Knowledge Newsletters, Traditional Knowledge Websites, and Traditional Knowledge Literature (<http://www.kivu.com/world-council-guidelines/>)

National Resources:

Norway

- The Sami Act: <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/the-sami-act/id449701/>
- Nature Diversity Act (2009): <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/nature-diversity-act/id570549/>
- SoriaMoria Declaration : <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/the-soria-moria-declaration-on-internati/id438515/>
- High North Strategy (2006): <https://www.regjeringen.no/globalassets/upload/ud/vedlegg/strategien.pdf>
- "New building blocks in the North" (2009): https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/north_blocks/id548803/

- **Finland**

- The Sámi in Legislation - the constitution in Finland :
http://www.samediggi.fi/index.php?option=com_content&task=blogcategory&id=87&Itemid=106

- **Greenland**

- Greenland Parliament <http://cms.inatsisartut.gl/om-inatsisartut.aspx?lang=en>
- The Inuit Circumpolar Council – Based in Greenland and representing Inuit Alaska, Canada, and Chukotka, Russia. (<http://www.inuit.org/>)

3. Summary and Recommendations

The APECS Nordic Project “Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Regions” has presented a broad review of the current climate in Nordic research, and where the opportunities are to bridge any existing gaps between researchers (indigenous and non-indigenous) and indigenous communities. Through the workshop, survey, and seminars, it is evident that the researchers, indigenous communities and indigenous community researchers hold many of the answers and recommendations themselves. The recommendations provided below are summarized from those insights presented by these stakeholders throughout the project.

Recommendations

- Researchers and educational institutions should assume greater responsibility to become informed and knowledgeable about community history, norms, expectations and concerns prior to field work
- Educational Institutions should provide/create policy ensuring training of local research participants to ensure mutual benefits
- Indigenous community members should become research partners and ensure local indigenous knowledge integration in the research project/plan from the outset.
- Researchers and community members should be mindful of different worldviews or epistemologies through all phases of research project.
- Research funding institutions should account for a long field season, return visits, compensation for local indigenous research partners, interview informants, costs of translations, interpreters as well as dissemination of results in all Nordic research.
- Strive for research sustainability or longevity of research initiatives to promote synthesis of research projects and results.

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5. Appendix

5.1. APECS Nordic Workshop 2014 Programme

5.2. APECS Nordic Workshop materials

5.2.1. Breakout Session Questions & Responses Booklet

5.2.2. Breakout Sessions Facilitation & Discussion Guide

5.3. APECS Nordic Survey (English Version)

5.3.1. For Early Career Researchers

5.3.2. For Indigenous peoples in Northern communities

5.1. APECS Nordic Workshop Program

APECS NORDIC WORKSHOP, 7-8 APRIL 2014

*Connecting Early Career Researchers and Community Driven
Research in the North*

Arctic Summit Science Week
Helsinki, Finland

Part of the *Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries* Research Project

WELCOME!

Welcome to the **Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)** Nordic Connecting Early Career Researchers and Community Driven Research in the North Workshop!

We are thrilled to have you a part of this significant and timely event. We hope that you leave here with valuable insight into how research in Nordic countries amongst Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples can be enhanced. Thank you for your input and contributions. Results will be summarized and made available in the Nordic languages in fall 2014.

Thank you for attending the Workshop!

ABOUT THE APECS NORDIC PROJECT

APECS is an international and interdisciplinary organization for individuals (undergraduates and graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, early career faculty members, educators, others) with interests in Polar Regions and the wider cryosphere. APECS is dedicated to stimulating interdisciplinary and international research collaborations and developing future leaders in polar research, education, and outreach. One of APECS initiatives is the 18-month project called “Bridging Polar Early Career Researchers (ECRs) and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries.” This project aims to facilitate meaningful interaction and efficient collaborative work between polar ECRs and Northern Indigenous peoples, among which Sami people are a key focus. The long-term project goal is to improve knowledge on Arctic environments, as a base for future sustainable development strategies in the Nordic region. The main objectives of the project include:

- Strengthen the Nordic network of polar ECRs and young Indigenous peoples living in different parts of the Nordic region;
- Identify current challenges in the communication between researchers and Indigenous peoples;
- Provide case-studies and training for ECRs in incorporating Traditional Knowledge into research practices;
- Provide relevant information and tools for ECRs and Indigenous peoples through a series of online webinars and an in-person workshop;
- Develop and archive a digital library of resources from webinars, workshop outcomes, and existing tools to support ECR engagement with Indigenous youth in the Nordic countries and support Indigenous youth involvement in research projects conducted in their communities and on their lands

ABOUT THE APECS NORDIC WORKSHOP

A major component of the APECS Nordic project is this 2-day workshop entitled “Connecting early career researchers and community driven research in the north” in conjunction with the Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW), organized by the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) in Helsinki. The goal of the workshop is to help facilitate communication, understanding, and connections between ECRs, Indigenous Peoples, and local Traditional Knowledge experts. This workshop includes: informative presentations, in-depth discussions in break out groups, and information sharing and introduction to the Nordic Project Survey. The following products will be result from this workshop and are expected to be a major outcome of the project:

- Summary report and guide for polar ECRs on the communication with Indigenous peoples in the Nordic region;
- Summary report and guide for ECRs on the integration of Traditional Knowledge into research practices;
- Publically accessible archive of all the APECS Nordic project materials including webinars, summarized survey results, database and the workshop summary report.
- A set of recommendations Indigenous youths can use to engage in and/or develop Northern research programs.

All resources will be developed in English and translated into the following Nordic languages (Northern Sami, Swedish, Norwegian, Danish, Finnish and Russian).

These resources will be made available on the APECS website, shared with workshop and project participants, and presented at relevant conferences and meetings during 2014-2015.

Learn more about the APECS Nordic Project at www.apecs.is/apecs-norden.

Follow APECS on Twitter **@polar_research**

Live tweet during the workshop **#APECSNordic**

WORKSHOP SCHEDULE

	Monday, April 7, 2014	Tuesday, April 8, 2014
9:00-09:30	Welcome & Introductions Laura Fleming-Sharp Gerlis Fugmann, APECS	Welcome & Recap Laura Fleming-Sharp
09:30-09:50	LARS-ANDERS BAER Nordic Saami Council	HEIDI ERIKSEN Utsjoki Health Center
09:50-10:10	ARJA RAUTIO Thule Institute	ANNA AFANASYEVA International Barents Secretariat
10:10-10:30	ROBERT DELGADO JR University of Southern California/NSF	GAIL FONDAHL University of Northern British Columbia
10:30-11:00	COFFEE BREAK	COFFEE BREAK
11:00-11:30	IASC Presentation: ICARP III David Hik, ICARP Chair	<i>Theme: Successful collaboration models, building a community & broader impacts</i>
11:30-12:30	<i>Theme: Stakeholders & policies for working with Indigenous groups</i> Break Out Group 1 Room: Tellus, Dynamicum	Break Out Group 1 Room: Tellus, Dynamicum
	Break Out Group 2 Room: Brainstorm, Dynamicum	Break Out Group 2 Room: Brainstorm, Dynamicum
12:30-14:00	LUNCH	LUNCH
	Break Out Group 3 Room: Tellus, Dynamicum	Break Out Group 3 Room: Tellus, Dynamicum
	Break Out Group 4 Room: Brainstorm, Dynamicum	Break Out Group 4 Room: Brainstorm, Dynamicum
15:30-16:00	COFFEE BREAK	COFFEE BREAK
16:00-16:30	Report out session: Sharing results from breakout session	Report out session: Sharing results from breakout session
16:30-17:30	Nordic Survey Ylva Sjöberg & Sarah Nuernberger	
17:00-17:30	Summary & Goals for Day 2 Laura Lukes	Workshop Exit Survey Sandra Juutilainen
17:30	End for day	End Workshop
18:00	ASSW Reception Helsinki City Hall APECS Finland Social Event (Location to be confirmed)	

VENUE KEY

Brainstorm Room, Dynamicum Building
Tellus Room, Dynamicum Building
Off Site
Breaks
Mare Room, Dynamicum Building (only if needed)

WORKSHOP VENUES

Dynamicum Building

Physicum Building

MEET THE APECS NORDIC PROJECT TEAM

Gerlis Fugmann, APECS Director, Project Manager

Gerlis Fugmann, APECS Director, has been actively involved in the APECS leadership for several years. She completed her PhD in Geography at the Justus Liebig University Giessen in Germany in 2011 and worked afterwards for two years as a post-doctoral researcher at the International Centre for Northern Governance and Development (ICNGD) at the University of Saskatchewan in Canada. Her research focused on the Canadian Arctic and Sub-Arctic as well as Northern Scandinavia, addressing questions of comparative economic development, entrepreneurship, tourism, resource development and Northern engagement and participation in innovation and the knowledge economy. Gerlis has served on the Executive Committee from 2009-2011 and as APECS President during the 2009 – 2010 term.

Laura Fleming-Sharp, Project Coordinator, USA

Laura Fleming-Sharp, is a Research Assistant at the Arctic Studies Center at the National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution. Laura's research focuses on human-environment interactions and climate change adaptation. She contributed to a 2007-2009 IPY Community Adaptation and Vulnerability in the Arctic Regions (CAVIAR) project, and for two Arctic Net Projects. Laura worked as a Research Associate at the Global Environmental Change Group (GECG) in the Department of Geography, University of Guelph. In October 2012 Laura was one of the Coordinators for the 18th Inuit Studies Conference, hosted by the Arctic Studies Center at the Smithsonian.

WORKSHOP COMMITTEE

Laura Lukes, Workshop Committee Co-Chair, USA

Laura Lukes is part of the Geoscience Learning Process Research Group at North Carolina State University (NCSU) where her research focuses on capturing the student experience in introductory geology courses with the aim of recruiting and retaining a more diverse STEM workforce. She currently teaches an introductory Physical Geology lecture course at NCSU and several online geology courses for Rio Salado Community College. She organized and led the Joint Science Education Project (JSEP), an international science education field research experience for teachers and students from Greenland, Denmark, and the U.S. on the ice sheet in Greenland. For JSEP, she recruited and coordinated 30+ scientist mentors from over 15 domestic and international institutions and government agencies to work with students in the field.

Sarah Nuernberger, Survey Committee Member, USA

Sarah Nuernberger holds a MA in International Development from the University of Denver's Josef Korbel School of International Studies in Denver, Colorado, USA, with concentrations in GIS, water and natural resource management, and geopolitics. Her research interests broadly focus on the interactions of humans, the environment, and policy, specifically with regard to the impacts of climate change and resource development in the Polar Regions. Sarah is currently the Product Development Specialist at iDE - International Development Enterprises, a non-profit working with smallholder farmers in developing countries. When not working or traveling, you can find Sarah climbing, hiking, camping, skiing, or snowshoeing in the Rocky Mountains.

Ylva Sjöberg, Survey Committee Chair, Sweden

Ylva Sjöberg is a physical geography doctoral student at Stockholm University and coordinator of the Swedish branch of the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) international network. Her PhD project focuses on exploring the interactions between permafrost and groundwater, which is crucial for understanding future changes that can be expected in the Arctic with climate warming. The aim is to assess the effects of permafrost thaw on hydrology both at a detailed and process-oriented scale, and at catchment scales. This is done by analyzing long-term river discharge data, field mapping of ground-ice using geophysical methods, and physically-based modeling of coupled groundwater flows and heat transport. Ylva is APECS' representative to the IPA Education and Outreach Committee and the the organizing committee of the upcoming Permafrost Young Researchers' workshop at EUCOP4 in Évora, Portugal 2014.

WEBINARS COMMITTEE

Yulia Zaika, Webinars Committee Co-Chair, Russia

Yulia was born in Murmansk region of NW Russia on May 14, 1984. I completed my studies at Petrozavodsk State University as Ecologist and Interpreter in 2006. Currently I am a Research Assistant at Khibiny educational and scientific base of the Faculty of Geography M.V.Lomonosov Moscow State University. My research focuses on observations of climate data, snow cover and avalanches as natural hazardous processes in highly industrialized Russian Arctic regions. Since 2007 I was involved in IPY PPS Arctic project as a member of Benefits Russian Team ("Natural and Social Science Research Cooperation in Northern Russia and Norway for Mutual Benefits across National and Scientific Borders") and coordinator for socially oriented observations on

quality of life of people in Murmansk region. At the moment I am involved as Khibiny base representative in EU 7 Framework Programme project INTERACT (International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic) with a numerous of circumarctic field station partners from 18 countries.

Jocelyn Torma, Webinars Committee Co-Chair, Canada

Jocelyn Torma is currently a graduate student at the University of Waterloo. Her work in the department of Philosophy aims at developing methods of intercultural understanding to improve current co-operative strategy for sustainable development in Canada. She has done research on the relationship between the arts and the economy in urban areas, especially in Northern Canada. In her home town of Thunder Bay, she enjoyed being an advocate of the unique local arts and culture scene that thrives there.

DATABASE COMMITTEE

Julia Skupchenko, Database Developer, Russia

Julia Skupchenko is completing her Master's student in Political Sciences at Syktyvkar State University (Russia). She holds a Bachelor degree in Circumpolar Studies from the University of the Arctic. She has been on exchange programs with the University of Nordland (Norway); the Northern British Columbia University (Canada) and Umea University (Sweden). Her research focus is on the Arctic stakeholders' cooperation, especially on the issue of resources exploration. For a year she has been an intern with the Arctic Theme of Shell International, the Netherlands, studying that topic. Right now she is an International Research Associate at Canadian Polar Commission focusing on the Russian Arctic and Indigenous Peoples of the Russian North. She also co-chaired scientific sessions at the Arctic Frontiers 2012 and the Arctic Science Summit Week 2013.

APECS Nordic Workshop Plenary Speakers

LARS-ANDERS BAER, NORDIC SAAMI COUNCIL, SWEDEN

Bio: As a member of the Saami Council, Mr. Baer was involved in the pan-Saami movement in the early the 1970's and was the chairman of the council when the Saami population in Russia was integrated into the pan-Saami movement during the glasnost period at the end of the 1980s. As a key figure in the Saami Council, he was also involved in setting up the development aid programme, which is an indigenous to indigenous programme in Latin America, Asia and Africa. Has been involved in the UN Working Group on Indigenous Populations from 1983 onwards.

ARJA RAUTIO, MD, PhD, ERT, CENTER FOR ARCTIC MEDICINE, THULE INSTITUTE, FINLAND

Bio: Arja Rautio, research professor, MD, PhD, ERT, has been working in the field of circumpolar health since 2006. She is a director of the Center for Arctic Medicine (www oulu.fi/arctichealth) at the Thule Institute (www oulu.fi/thule) in the University of Oulu (Finland). She is leading a PhD graduate program in the Thule Institute, several research projects and the international Master's program of Circumpolar Health and Wellbeing (<http://www oulu.fi/degree/hw>). She is a chair of the University of the Arctic Thematic Network of Health and Wellbeing in the Arctic (www.uarctic.org). Her research focuses are in climate change and human health, social exclusion and indigenous health and wellbeing.

PLENARY TITLE: *Opportunities for Early Career Researchers*

ABSTRACT: Collaboration and communication between the different organizations in the Arctic are necessary to reach the best results in our joint efforts to achieve a better quality of life for the people living in the Arctic. Early career researchers, PhD and Master's students, are a key group to integrate into the international research community. The different working groups of the Arctic Council are formed from the official nominated key experts representing eight Arctic countries, however for some of the working groups in the health sub-group of the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), the meetings are open for all. The Indigenous peoples' organizations are key elements in the work of Arctic Council and University of the Arctic. The University of the Arctic (UA) is working as a virtual university network among the circumpolar higher education institutes and universities. The thematic networks of the UA, like the Health and Well-being network, provide an excellent possibility for PhD students to take special field courses, summer/winter schools, and also participate in research projects and education. Within this

presentation will be a discussion of the active research societies and unions in different research fields where early career researchers are warmly welcomed to participate.

**ROBERTO DELGADO JR, PHD, DEPARTMENT OF BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES,
UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHERN CALIFORNIA, USA**

Bio: Dr. Roberto Delgado is currently an AAAS Science & Technology Policy Fellow at the National Science Foundation (NSF). He is a biological anthropologist with expertise in animal behavior, communication, and evolutionary ecology. While at Duke University, he examined the function of adult male long calls on social organization and reproductive strategies among wild orangutan populations in Borneo and Sumatra. His subsequent research while at Hunter College CUNY and USC addressed the demographic and ecological sources of behavioral flexibility, geographic variation, and local adaptation by non-human primates in response to anthropogenic threats and climate change. In addition to extensive fieldwork throughout the Neotropics, Southeast Asia, and sub-Saharan Africa, Roberto is actively involved in wildlife conservation and management issues, and co-chairs the AAAS Biodiversity Affinity Group. He has worked closely with indigenous communities on land-use planning and population monitoring, and has policy interests in biodiversity, ecosystem services, environmental sustainability, international development, enhancing scientific literacy, and furthering minority representation in STEM fields.

At NSF, Roberto is working in the Division of Polar Programs, supporting the goals and activities of the Arctic Sciences Section. In this capacity, he is engaging with the US State Department in Joint Committee Meetings on Science & Technology Cooperation agreements with Arctic nations, working with the US Arctic Research Commission and Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC), serving as co-lead on the IARPC Arctic Communities Implementation Team, participating in the Arctic Policy Group, and contributing to international working groups on biodiversity and sustainable development for the Arctic Council.

PLENARY TITLE: *U.S. Agency Policies on Consultation with Arctic Indigenous Communities*

ABSTRACT: Mandated by the U.S. Arctic Research and Policy Act of 1984, the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC), chaired by the National Science Foundation, is charged with coordinating federal interagency research planning in the Arctic. I am conducting an exploratory review of federal agency policies on consultation with indigenous communities and an evaluation of the IARPC *Principles for the Conduct of Research in the Arctic*. These Principles, approved

in 1990 and published in 1995 in the Arctic Research Journal of the United States, were prepared by an Interagency Social Science Task Force in response to a recommendation by the Polar Research Board of the National Academy of Sciences and at the direction of IARPC. Specifically, the Principles emerged amid concern that science, engineering, and related activities sponsored and conducted by federal agencies would impact the lives of Native peoples in the Arctic. Hence, the aims of the review and evaluation are to determine the value and utility of these Principles and consultation policies, particularly as they relate to engagement with Arctic / Alaska Native communities, how agencies implement and comply with existing policies, and to develop best practice guidelines for community-based participatory research in the Arctic. I cite examples from selected U.S. federal agencies engaged in research and education activities with Alaska Native populations, and I assess the strengths and weaknesses of their consultation policies.

HEIDI ERIKSEN, MD, PHD, UTSJOKI HEALTH CENTRE, FINLAND

Bio: Heidi A. Eriksen, MD, PhD, is an indigenous Sámi, working as a general practitioner and chief medical officer in Utsjoki, her home and the northernmost municipality of Finland with indigenous Sámis as majority of population. She was raised in Utsjoki, having a river Sámi background. She has worked at the Utsjoki health care centre since 2005. After finishing

her doctoral thesis in a biochemical topic in 2010, her research interest has focused on the health, disease and wellbeing of Sámi and other indigenous peoples. This interest has risen through her basic work with the Sámi population and noticing the lack of stewardship of Sámi people in the health systems, lack of systematically collected data of the health issues and wellbeing of the Sámis. Heidi A. Eriksen has been an elected member of Sámi Parliament 2008-2011 and a member in the social and health board of Sámi Parliament 2008-2011 and 2012-2015. She has been a member of advisory boards of several projects concerning Sámi health and social issues.

PLENARY TITLE: *Research Ethics for Working with Sámi Peoples - The Case of Finland*

ABSTRACT: In both building the health care system and doing research among indigenous communities, the values, needs and interests of these groups tend to be forgotten. Some good examples of taking into account these aspects are found around the world, however, even though Finland has numerous research-ethical legislations and guidelines (see www.aka.fi), there is a lack of ethical principles when working with Sámi communities. In addition, although the need for cultural sensitive services and linguistic rights of Sámi people has been recognized, even at the ministry level, however, there have not been real efforts to promote these needs. Historically, research conducted 'on' Indigenous peoples worldwide has not always

been conducted in an ethical manner or with the communities' interests in mind, and Finland is no exception to this fact. More researchers are becoming increasingly interested in the Arctic and working in areas where Sámi people reside. Therefore, with this increase in research activity has also produced an ongoing dialogue among non-Sámi and Sámi scholars about the need to develop guidelines for working with Sámi in Finland. Examples of guidelines and policies from Canada, Australia and New Zealand can provide a starting point to developing guidelines in Finland for working 'with' Sámi communities. However, the core philosophies and meanings of the guidelines should be rooted in Sámi ways of knowing and being and include consultation with a variety of Sámi stakeholders. The goal of this presentation is to discuss historical interactions with researchers and Sámi communities in Finland, the current situation of Sámi peoples' rights in the health care system, the influence and increasing numbers of Sámi scholars and some suggestions for moving forward in developing the guidelines.

ANNA AFANASYEVA, INDIGENOUS PEOPLES ADVISER, INTERNATIONAL BARENTS SECRETARIAT, NORWAY

Bio: Anna Afanasyeva is currently working as Indigenous Peoples Adviser at the International Barents Secretariat (IBS), in Kirkenes, Norway. In spring 2013 defended the Master of Philosophy in Indigenous Studies at the Arctic University of Tromsø on the topic of Forced relocations of the Kola Sámi people: background and consequences, in which discusses implementation of the Soviet policies of forced relocations as associated with the new society-building patterns, restructuring traditional economies and need for active cultural and language preservation for the Kola Sámi today. In the years 2006 – 2010 worked in the field of endangered languages documentation as a student assistant in the research project - Kola Saami Documentation project, based at Department of Northern European Studies, Humboldt University, in Berlin, mainly dealing with fieldwork activity, creating audio recordings of Sámi speakers, annotation and preparation of documented language materials for linguistic analyses. From summer 2014 will be working as P.h.D scholar supported by the Research Council of Norway at the Centre for Sámi Studies, at the Arctic University of Tromsø. The topic of the study will be devoted to analysis of the Assimilation policies in education imposed on the Kola Sámi in 1900's – 2010's. I am a Kola Sámi myself, that is why I found research in indigenous communities accounting on the needs and interests of its community members to be extremely important.

PLENARY TITLE: *Research from the point of view of an indigenous community insider: "Resettlement of Indigenous peoples in the Arctic- a case study of the Sámi people on the Kola Peninsula, Russia".*

ABSTRACT: The presentation will outline my general thoughts and considerations about the possible ways of cooperation between researchers and indigenous peoples as well as indigenous and non- indigenous researchers. I will also touch upon my experiences of the best practices on training local indigenous representatives in order to enter the academia, from my own example.

My published Master's thesis describes and analyses the background and consequences of the relocation policies imposed on the Kola Sámi people, in the North-West of Russia. The decades of relocations represent a turning point in history of the Sámi community as associated with the new society-building patterns, restructuring traditional economies and need for active cultural and language preservation today.

The Kola Sámi community faced the loss of their resource territories, disruption of traditional activities' practice along with strong influences of multicultural environment on language and culture as the impacts of forced relocation policies. The change in geographical distribution of the Sámi settlements has also caused shifts in communities' social organization and land use patterns. The thesis addresses implementation of the Soviet policies of forced relocations on the Kola Sámi people and touches upon the occurred consequences.

In my Master's study I focus on the experiences of the community members and on my vision as the community insider. I myself have a Sámi background and belong to the Kola Sámi community. My family and ancestors have experienced the policies of relocations and were resettled from their traditional territories.

In addition to presenting the mentioned above research results, I would like to concentrate on two aspects in this presentation. Firstly, share my ideas on how researchers can make "feedback to community" they are working in, and secondly, to present the examples of successful research projects, which I have been personally involved in as an indigenous academic trainee.

GAIL FONDAHL, PHD, UNIVERSITY OF NORTHERN BRITISH COLUMBIA, CANADA

Bio: Gail Fondahl is a Professor of Geography at the University of Northern British Columbia, Canada's northernmost research university. She currently serves as the president of the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (2011-2014). As well, she is Canada's representative to, and Vice-Chair of, the International Arctic Science Committee's Social & Human Sciences Working Group (2011-2015), and Chair of the Social, Economic and Cultural Expert Group of the Arctic Council's Sustainable Development Working Group (2013-2015). Gail's research has focused the legal geographies of indigenous rights to land in the Russian North, the historical geography of reindeer husbandry in the Russian North, and co-management of resources and of research in northern British Columbia.

DAY 1 - Breakout Groups

<i>Group 1 & 3 (Tellus Room)</i> <i>Moderators: Laura Lukes & Sandra Juutilainen</i>		<i>Group 2 & 4 (Brainstorm Auditorium)</i> <i>Moderators: Julie Bull & Laura Fleming-Sharp</i>	
Afanasyeva, Anna	Kivinen, Sonja	Jones, Chas	Rautio, Arja
Albov, Sophia	Ksenofontov, Stanislav	Järvinen, Onni	Ross, Jeffrey
Azinhaga, Patricia	Kuznetsova, Elena	Kivelä, Tiina	Kivinen, Sonja
Boulanger, Lapointe Noemie	Logvinova, Christie	Roy, Louis-Philippe	Väisänen, Maria
Choy, Emily	Lys, Candice	Sjöberg, Ylva	Waksman, Laura
Delgado, Roberto	Majaneva, Sanna	Skupchenko, Julia	Green, Emily
De Palaminy, Adèle	Majaneva, Markus	Smieszek, Malgorzata	Raturi, Dhruv
Egelkraut, Dagmar	Mortensen, Lars O.	Strecker, Lisa	Alvarado, Nikolai
Gordon, Heather	Nuernberger, Sarah	Strauss-Mazzullo, Hannah	Varfolomeeva, Anna
Horstkotte, Tim	Paglia, Erik	Suprenand, Paul	Wickström, Siiri
Hoset, Katrine	Paradis, Marney	Tuomi, Maria	Lehtinen, Taru
Jokivirta, Lisa	Pirazzini, Roberta	Zaika, Yuliya	Bourgain, Pascaline
		Jackson, M.	Holak, Irene
		Baer, Lars-Anders	Shavrina, Olga

DAY 2 - Breakout Groups

<i>Group 1 & 3 (Tellus Room)</i> <i>Moderators: Sandra Juutilainen & Laura Fleming-Sharp</i>		<i>Group 2 & 4 (Brainstorm Auditorium)</i> <i>Moderators: Julie Bull & Laura Lukes</i>	
Afanasyeva, Anna	Kivinen, Sonja	Jokivirta, Lisa	Azinhaga, Patricia
Shavrina, Olga	Rautio, Arja	Järvinen, Onni	Ross, Jeffrey
Suprenand, Paul	Kuznetsova, Elena	Horstkotte, Tim	Kivinen, Sonja
Alvarado, Nikolai	Logvinova, Christie	Nuernberger, Sarah	Väisänen, Maria
Choy, Emily	Lys, Candice	Sjöberg, Ylva	Waksman, Laura
Smieszek, Malgorzata	Majaneva, Sanna	Mortensen, Lars O.	Albov, Sophia
De Palaminy, Adèle	Majaneva, Markus	Ksenofontov, Stanislav	Raturi, Dhruv
Wickström, Siiri	Green, Emily	Strecker, Lisa	Jones, Chas
Gordon, Heather	Skupchenko, Julia	Strauss-Mazzullo, Hannah	Varfolomeeva, Anna
Roy, Louis-Philippe	Paglia, Erik	Egelkraut, Dagmar	Boulanger, Lapointe Noemie
Hoset, Katrine	Paradis, Marney	Tuomi, Maria	Lehtinen, Taru
Kivelä, Tiina	Pirazzini, Roberta	Zaika, Yuliya	Bourgain, Pascaline
		Jackson, M.	Holak, Irene
		Baer, Lars-Anders	Delgado, Roberto

Note: If you do not see your name listed, please join the [Brainstorm Room](#) Group.

Format: Each breakout session will have 2 moderators to ensure everyone has an equal opportunity to contribute and a recorder to keep track of discussion to create a final list of considerations.

Break Out Group Discussion Questions: See Workshop Question Booklet.

Important: We encourage each participant to use the workshop question booklet to write down their thoughts and comments during the breakout discussions. These will be collected at the end of the workshop and used as additional source of input & contribution from workshop participants.

APECS NORDIC WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS LIST

As of 3.26.14

Afanasyeva	Anna	International Barents Secretariat	Norway
Albov	Sophia	Fulbright Student Grantee / University of Montana	Finland
Alvarado	Nikolai	University of Denver	USA
Azinhaga	Patrícia	University of Coimbra	Portugal
Boulanger-Lapointe	Noemie	University of British Columbia	Canada
Bourgain	Pascaline	Tara Expeditions	France
Bull	Julie	Toronto Aboriginal Support Services Council	Canada
Choy	Emily	University of Manitoba	Canada
Delgado	Roberto	AAAS / NSF	USA
DE PALAMINY	Adèle	Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle	France
Egelkraut	Dagmar	Umeå University	Sweden
Fugmann	Gerlis	APECS / University of Tromsø	Norway
Gordon	Heather	University of Wisconsin-Madison	USA
Green	Emily	University of Denver	USA
Holak	Irene	Antioch University New England	USA
Horstkotte	Tim	University of Turku	Finland

Hoset	Katrine	University of Turku	Finland
Jackson	Jerilynn "M"	University of Oregon / National Geographic	USA
Järvinen	Onni	University of Helsinki	Finland
Jokivirta	Lisa	University of Jyväskylä	Finland
Jones	Chas	University of Alaska Fairbanks	USA
Juutilainen	Sandra	University of Oulu	Finland
Kivelä	Tiina	University of Lapland	Finland
Kivinen	Sonja	University of Turku	Finland
Ksenofontov	Stanislav	University of Zurich	Switzerland
Kuznetsova	Elena	SINTEF / NTNU	Norway
Lehtinen	Taru	University of Iceland	Austria
Logvinova	Christie	Clark University	USA
Lukes	Laura	North Carolina State University	USA
Lys	Candice	University of Toronto/Institute for Circumpolar Health Research	Canada
Majaneva	Sanna	University of Helsinki	Finland
Majaneva	Markus	University of Helsinki	Finland
Mortensen	Lars O.	Aarhus University	Denmark

Nuernberger	Sarah	iDE – International Development Enterprises	USA
Paglia	Eric	KTH / APECS Sweden	Sweden
Paradis	Marney	Simon Fraser University	Canada
Pienkowski	Anna	Bangor University, School of Ocean Sciences	United Kingdom
Pirazzini	Roberta	Finnish Meteorological Institute	Finland
Rautio	Arja	University of Oulu	Finland
Raturi	Dhruv	Physics Department, School of Arts and Science - University of Richmond	USA
Ross	Jeffrey	University of Utah	USA
Roy	Louis-Philippe	Northern Climate ExChange, Yukon Research Centre	Canada
Sharp	Laura	Arctic Studies Center, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution	USA
Shavrina	Olga	University of Tromsø	Norway
Sjöberg	Ylva	Stockholm University	Sweden
Skupchenko	Julia	Syktsu	Russian Federation
Smieszek	Malgorzata	University of Lapland	Finland
Strecker	Lisa	University of Alaska Fairbanks	USA
Strauss-Mazzullo	Hannah	Arctic Centre, University of Lapland	Finland
Suprenand	Paul	University of South Florida	USA

Tuomi	Maria	University of Turku	Finland
Väisänen	Maria	University of Lapland	Finland
Varfolomeeva	Anna	Uppsala Centre for Russian and Eurasian Studies	Sweden
Vos	Matthew	North Slope Science Initiative	USA
Waksman	Laura	University of Denver	USA
Wickström	Siiri	University of Helsinki	Finland
Zaika	Yuliya	Lomonosov Moscow State University (Khibiny scientific station)	Russia

Thank you for participating in the APECS Nordic Workshop!

WWW.APECS.IS/APECS-Norden

5.2. APECS Nordic Workshop Materials

5.2.1. Breakout Session Questions & Responses Booklet

**APECS Nordic Workshop, ASSW - April 7,8 2014
Breakout Sessions Questions & Responses Booklet**

DAY 1: Theme 1- Guidelines/policies for working with indigenous groups

1. What are the current policies & protocols for working with indigenous peoples in Nordic regions?

2. Who are the stakeholders?

3. What are the stakeholder needs?

4. What are the needs of indigenous peoples in Nordic regions?

5. What are the needs of early career researchers?

1. What is missing? Where are the gaps? Where do we go from here?

Day 2: Theme2- Effective communication skills

2. What is effective communication?

8. How does communication take place in Nordic research currently? Elsewhere?

9. What could be improved in Nordic communication? What is working well?

Theme 3: Successful collaboration efforts w/ indigenous groups

10. What makes a “successful” collaboration?

11. What are the needs of researchers and indigenous populations?

12. What research & communication strategies support success?

13. What is a best-case scenario/example of successful research collaboration?

14. What does a non-indigenous researcher need to be aware of?

Theme 4: Broader Impacts-Communicating results and outreach

15. How do you communicate your project/research interests? Your results?

16. How can research results be best communicated within indigenous groups?

17. How can research results be best communicated across the Arctic?

Additional Thoughts or Comments:

5.2.2. Breakout Sessions Facilitation & Discussion Guide

**APECS Nordic Workshop
Breakout Sessions Facilitation & Discussion Guide
Day 1 & 2
April 7,8 2014**

DAY 1: Introductions & Theme 1- Guidelines/policies for working with indigenous groups

Break out session 1: 11:30am-12:30pm

Introductions

1. Introduce ourselves as the breakout session facilitators. Each facilitator should tell a bit about their area of work/study, and what brought you to the project.

2. Ask participants to pair off and take some time to introduce each other. After 10-15 minutes, ask that each participant introduce each other to the group. We can provide a list of questions for them to ask each other that are relevant to the workshop to help draw that information out of each person. We could do groups of 2 or 4.

3. Once everyone has been introduced, and everyone has finished discussions, Introduce the theme for the day. Explain the goal for the end of the day, mention the main themes, and then break for lunch.

-What are the current policies & protocols for working with indigenous peoples in Nordic regions?

-Who are the stakeholders?

-What are the stakeholder needs?

Break out session 2: 2:00pm-3:30pm

Guidelines/policies for working with Indigenous groups

1. Are there current policies & protocols for working with indigenous peoples in Nordic regions?
2. What are they?
3. Who are the stakeholders?
4. What are the stakeholder needs?
 - a. What are the needs of indigenous peoples in Nordic regions?
 - b. What are the needs of early career researchers?
 - c. What is missing? Where are the gaps? Where do we go from here?

**APECS Nordic Workshop
Breakout Sessions Facilitation & Discussion Guide**

Day 2: Theme 2, 3 & 4

11:00am-12:30pm - Theme 1 Effective communication skills

1. Introduce the themes for the day
2. Explain the two break out group session themes and the focus of each.
3. Begin discussion by asking the whole group the following first question:

What is effective communication?

4. Write down responses as participants respond- ask for keywords, outcomes, process, approaches, etc.
5. Once there is a good list going, ask people to break out into groups to discuss the next questions:

How does communication take place in Nordic research currently? Elsewhere?

What could be improved in Nordic communication?

What is working well?

6. Ask that groups report out their discussion results.
7. Include a few slides on tips at communicating at this point (time permitting).

Continue to theme 3: Successful collaboration efforts w/ indigenous groups

8. Discuss together as a whole group:

What makes a “successful” collaboration?

What are the needs of researchers and indigenous populations?

2:00pm-4:00pm - Theme 3 (Continued) & Theme 4: Broader Impacts:

9. Continue theme 3 questions:
10. Ask participants to write down their thoughts on their own to the following questions:

What research & communication strategies support success?

What is a best-case scenario/example of successful research collaboration?

11. Discuss & note responses.
12. As a whole group, ask for thoughts on the following question:

What does a non-indigenous researcher need to be aware of?

13. Move on to theme 4.

Theme 4: Broader Impacts-Communicating results and outreach

14. In small groups, then as a whole group, discuss the following questions:

How do you communicate your results?

How can we best communicate results within indigenous groups?

How can we best communicate results across the Arctic?

5.3. APECS Nordic Survey (English version)

The survey in the other languages can be accessed on the survey website <http://tinyurl.com/apecs-nordic-survey-2014>

5.3.1. For Early Career Researchers

Norden APECS Project Survey - Early Career Researchers

This survey is part of the APECS Norden Project entitled 'Bridging Polar Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries'. This 14-month research project funded by Norden aims at facilitating efficient and meaningful interaction and work between polar early career scientists (ECRs) and Northern Indigenous people among which Sami people are a focus of the project. The long-term goal is to improve knowledge on Arctic environments as a base for future sustainable development strategies in the region.

This particular survey aims at mapping existing interactions between indigenous people and ECRs as well as expectations, needs, and challenges for successful interactions and collaborations between these two groups.

Two versions of the survey are available: one for researchers and one for indigenous people. Indigenous people who are also researchers can choose to fill in either of the surveys or both.

At the end of the survey, you have the option to fill in your email address to receive information about the results and outcomes of the survey.

For more information about this survey and the project, please consult the project web page:

http://www.apecs.nl/index.php?title=Home_center&user=category&page=40&id=6753&theme=719

1. I am:

- A Polar researcher
- An Indigenous person
- Both of the above

2. Gender

- Male
- Female

3. Age Group

- Under 18
- 18-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- Over 45

4. Educational Background

- Below Bachelor level
- Bachelor level
- Master level
- PhD
- Post-Doc
- Other: _____

5. Current Occupation

- Undergraduate student
- Master student
- PhD student
- Researcher
- Other: _____

6. Research Field

- Atmosphere and Climate
- Marine
- Education and Outreach
- Language and Culture
- Art and Archaeology
- Terrestrial
- Human and Social Development
- Health and Food Security
- Cryosphere
- Other: _____

7. Within your current research project, please indicate what is your role.

- Researcher
- Field work assistant
- Interviewer
- Traditional knowledge expert
- Translator/interpreter
- Project coordinator
- Other: _____

8. Please indicate the geographic location in latitude/longitude of your research area.

How to find Your location on Google: 1. Go to <http://maps.google.com/maps>. 2. Type your location in the search bar. 3. Right click on the pin that appears on the map. 4. Select "What's Here?". 5. Your latitude/longitude will appear in the search bar as a string of numbers separated by a comma. 6. Copy and paste this into the box below. Alternatively, please simply indicate your location.

9. Please indicate the geographic location in latitude/longitude where you live.

How to find Your location on Google: 1. Go to <http://maps.google.com/maps>. 2. Type your location in the search bar. 3. Right click on the pin that appears on the map. 4. Select "What's Here?". 5. Your latitude/longitude will appear in the search bar as a string of numbers separated by a comma. 6. Copy and paste this into the box below. Alternatively, please simply indicate your location.

10. Level of experience in the field of Polar Research

- 1-3 Years
- 3-5 Years
- 5-10 Years
- More than 10 Years

Experience and perceptions

11. According to you, why is research about arctic areas important?

- To contribute to the sustainable development in the Arctic.
- To establish a basic understanding of natural and social systems.
- To improve living conditions and standard of living in the Arctic.
- To preserve indigenous cultures and communities.
- Other: _____

12. What is your level of experience working with indigenous people?

Please rate from 1=0, 1=No experience, 2=some minor experience, 3=some experience, 4=lot of experience, 5=all my research involves working with indigenous communities.

1 2 3 4 5

None All my research involves working with indigenous communities.

13. Have you ever involved local indigenous people in your research projects?

Please choose yes or no.

- Yes
- No

13. b) If yes to the previous question, please indicate in which capacity.

- Research design
- Outreach activities
- Field work
- Other: _____

13. c) If you have some working experience with indigenous people, please indicate if:

- You took the initiative yourself.
- It was imposed by your research.
- Both has occurred

14. a) As a polar researcher, I feel that I have a good understanding of the local environment of my study area

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

Understanding at all An excellent understanding

14. b) As a polar researcher, I feel that I have a good understanding of the local history of my study area

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

Understanding at all An excellent understanding

14. c) As a polar researcher, I feel that I have a good understanding of the local culture and customs of my study area

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

Understanding at all An excellent understanding

14. d) As a polar researcher, I feel that I have a good understanding of research methodologies.

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

Understanding at all An excellent understanding

14. e) As a polar researcher, I feel that I have a good understanding of field safety and logistics.

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

14. e) As a polar researcher, I feel that I have a good understanding of field safety and logistics.

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

No understanding at all An excellent understanding

15. a) To which degree do you consider that Indigenous people have an understanding of their local environment?

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

No understanding at all An excellent understanding

15. b) To which degree do you consider that Indigenous people have an understanding of their local history?

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

No understanding at all An excellent understanding

15. c) To which degree do you consider that Indigenous people have an understanding of their local culture and customs?

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

No understanding at all An excellent understanding

15. d) To which degree do you consider that Indigenous people have an understanding of Western research methodology?

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

No understanding at all An excellent understanding

15. e) To which degree do you consider that Indigenous people have an understanding of field safety and logistics?

Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all, 2= some understanding, 3= a good understanding, 4= a very good understanding, 5= an excellent understanding

1 2 3 4 5

No understanding at all An excellent understanding

16. Involvement of local Indigenous people in research can be beneficial to my field of research.

Please rank on a scale from 1=5: 1= do not agree, 2= somewhat agree, 3= agree, 4= strongly agree, 5= very strongly agree

1 2 3 4 5

Do not agree Very strongly agree

17. The knowledge and experience of local indigenous people is generally an untapped resource in polar research.

Please rank on a scale from 1=5: 1= do not agree, 2= somewhat agree, 3= agree, 4= strongly agree, 5= very strongly agree

1 2 3 4 5

Do not agree Very strongly agree

18. The involvement of local indigenous people in research is essential for the sustainable development of the Arctic region.

Please rank on a scale from 1=5: 1= do not agree, 2= somewhat agree, 3= agree, 4= strongly agree, 5= very strongly agree

1 2 3 4 5

Do not agree Very strongly agree

19. I have experienced conflicts or frustration when working with indigenous people when conducting my research.

Please rank on a scale from 1=5: 1= do not agree, 2= somewhat agree, 3= agree, 4= strongly agree, 5= very strongly agree

1 2 3 4 5

Do not agree Very strongly agree

20. Based on your experience, please indicate your general degree of satisfaction when sharing and/or conducting research with indigenous communities.

Please rate from 1=5: 1 = not satisfied at all, 2 = somewhat satisfied, 3 = fairly satisfied, 4 = satisfied, 5 = very satisfied

1 2 3 4 5

Not satisfied at all Very satisfied

Future prospects and challenges

21. Do you feel that you have the basic knowledge of how to conduct research with Northern communities?

Please indicate yes or no.

- Yes
- No

21. b) If yes to the previous question, please specify.

22. What are your expectations when you involve indigenous people in your research?

Please indicate your thoughts in the box below:

23. Would you like to have more involvement of local indigenous people in your projects?

- Yes
- No

23. b) If yes to the previous question, please indicate in which capacity.

- Research design
- Outreach activities
- Field work
- Other: _____

23. c) In order to involve local indigenous people in your research, what would you need?

- More contacts and opportunities to network
- More ideas and inspiration
- More time
- Financial resources
- More knowledge of traditional/indigenous knowledge and culture
- Other: _____

24. How would you like to share your research results with indigenous communities?

25. How does working with Northern communities benefit your research?

- Provide a better understanding of local environment
- Provide a better understanding of local history
- Provide better field safety
- Avoid conflicts with local people
- Increase outreach
- Other: _____

26. What challenges do you see when (considering) working in the areas of indigenous Peoples?

- Lack of communication/traction
- Cultural differences
- Language differences/barriers
- Lack of interest
- Lack of time
- Different analytical thinking/methodologies (i.e. concept of ecosystems)
- Other: _____

27. Based on your observations and experience, what elements would contribute to establish fruitful cooperation with between polar ECRs and indigenous youths?

Please indicate your thoughts in the box below:

28. Other comments (on entire survey)

29. Would you like to receive information about the results and outcomes of this study?

If so please provide your email address in the box below:

5.3.2. For Indigenous peoples in Northern communities

Nordic APECS Project Survey - Indigenous in Northern Countries

This survey is part of the APECS Norden Project entitled 'Bridging Polar Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries'. This 14-month research project funded by Norden aims at facilitating efficient and meaningful interaction and work between polar early career scientists (ECRs) and Northern Indigenous people among which Sámi people are a focus of the project. The long-term goal is to improve knowledge on Arctic environments as a base for future sustainable development strategies in the region.

This particular survey aims at mapping existing interactions between indigenous people and ECRs as well as expectations, needs, and challenges for successful interactions and collaborations between these two groups.

Two versions of this survey are available: one for researchers and one for indigenous people. Indigenous people who are also researchers can choose to fill in either of the surveys or both.

At the end of the survey, you have the option to fill your email address to receive information about the results and outcomes of the survey.

For more information about this survey and the project, please consult the project web page <http://www.apecs.norden.org/norden.com/content/view/full/1733.html#170>

- 1. I am**
- A polar researcher
 - An indigenous person
 - Both of the above

- 2. Gender**
- Male
 - Female

- 3. Age Group**
- Under 15
 - 15-25
 - 26-35
 - 36-45
 - Over 45

- 4. Educational background**
- Below bachelors level
 - Bachelor level
 - Master level
 - PhD
 - Post-Doc
 - Other: _____

- 5. Current Occupation**
- Undergraduate student
 - Master student
 - PhD student
 - Researcher
 - Other: _____

- 6. Research Field**
- Atmosphere and Climate
 - Marine
 - Education and Outreach
 - Language and Culture
 - Art and Archaeology
 - Marine
 - Terrestrial
 - Human and Social Development
 - Health and Food Security
 - Cryosphere
 - Other: _____

- 6. Research Field**
- Atmosphere and Climate
 - Marine
 - Education and Outreach
 - Language and Culture
 - Art and Archaeology
 - Marine
 - Terrestrial
 - Human and Social Development
 - Health and Food Security
 - Cryosphere
 - Other: _____

- 7. Within your current research project, please indicate what is your role.**
- Researcher
 - Field work assistant
 - Interviewer
 - Traditional knowledge expert
 - Translator/interpreter
 - Project coordinator
 - Other: _____

- 8. Please indicate the geographic location in latitude/longitude of your research area.**
How to Find Your Location on Google: 1. Go to <https://www.google.com/maps> 2. Type your location in the search bar 3. Right click on the pin that appears on the map 4. Select 'What's Here?' 5. Your latitude/longitude will appear in the search bar as a string of numbers separated by a comma. 6. Copy and paste this into the box below. Alternatively, please simply indicate your location.

- 9. Please indicate the geographic location in latitude/longitude where you live.**
How to Find Your Location on Google: 1. Go to <https://www.google.com/maps> 2. Type your location in the search bar 3. Right click on the pin that appears on the map 4. Select 'What's Here?' 5. Your latitude/longitude will appear in the search bar as a string of numbers separated by a comma. 6. Copy and paste this into the box below. Alternatively, please simply indicate your location.

- 10. Level of experience in the field of Polar Research**
- 1-3 Years
 - 3-5 Years
 - 5-10 Years
 - More than 10 Years

Experience and perceptions

- 11. According to you, why is research about arctic areas important?**
- To contribute to the sustainable development in the arctic.
 - To establish a basic understanding of natural and social systems.
 - To improve living conditions and standard of living in the Arctic.
 - To preserve indigenous cultures and communities.
 - Other: _____

- 12. What is your level of experience working with Polar researchers?**
Please rate from 1-5: 1= None 2= some minor experience 3= some experience 4= lot of experience 5= all my work involves polar researchers.
- 1 2 3 4 5
- None all my work involves polar researchers

- 13. Have you ever been involved in a Polar research project?**
Please answer yes or no.
- Yes
 - No

- 13. b) If yes, please indicate in which capacity.**
- Research design
 - Outreach activities
 - Field work
 - Other: _____

- 13. c) If you have some working experience with polar researchers, please indicate if:**
- You took the initiative yourself
 - It was imposed by your research
 - Both has occurred

- 14. a) As an indigenous person, I feel that I have a good understanding of the local environment of my study area/ the area where I live.**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 14. b) As an indigenous person, I feel that I have a good understanding of the local history of my study area/ the area where I live.**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 14. c) As an indigenous person, I feel that I have a good understanding of the local culture and customs of my study area/ the area where I live.**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 14. d) As an indigenous person, I feel that I have a good understanding of research methodology.**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 14. e) As an indigenous person, I feel that I have a good understanding of field safety and logistics.**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 15. a) Within their research work, would you say that polar researchers have a good understanding of the local environment?**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 15. b) Within their research work, would you say that polar researchers have a good understanding of the local history?**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 15. c) Within their research work, would you say that polar researchers have a good understanding of local cultures and customs?**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- No understanding at all
 - An excellent understanding

- 15. d) Within their research work, would you say that polar researchers have a good understanding of research methodology?**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 15. e) Within their research work, would you say that polar researchers have a good understanding of field safety and logistics?**
Please rank on a scale of 1 to 5: 1= no understanding at all 2= some understanding 3= a good understanding 4= a very good understanding 5= an excellent understanding
- 1 2 3 4 5
- No understanding at all An excellent understanding

- 16. Involvement of local indigenous people in research can be beneficial to polar research.**
Please rank on a scale from 1-5: 1= do not agree 2= somewhat agree 3= agree 4= strongly agree 5= very strongly agree
- 1 2 3 4 5
- Do not agree at all Very strongly agree

- 17. The knowledge and experience of local indigenous people is generally an untapped resource in polar research.**
Please rank on a scale from 1-5: 1= do not agree 2= somewhat agree 3= agree 4= strongly agree 5= very strongly agree
- 1 2 3 4 5
- Do not agree at all Very strongly agree

- 18. The involvement of local indigenous people in research is essential for the sustainable development of the Arctic region.**
Please rank on a scale from 1-5: 1= do not agree 2= somewhat agree 3= agree 4= strongly agree 5= very strongly agree
- 1 2 3 4 5
- Do not agree at all Very strongly agree

- 19. I have experienced conflicts or frustration when working with polar researchers.**
Please rank on a scale from 1-5: 1= do not agree 2= somewhat agree 3= agree 4= strongly agree 5= very strongly agree
- 1 2 3 4 5
- Do not agree at all Very strongly agree

- 20. Based on your experience, please indicate your general degree of satisfaction when sharing and/or conducting research with polar researchers.**
Please rate from 1-5: 1= not satisfied at all 2= somewhat satisfied 3= fairly satisfied 4= satisfied 5= very satisfied
- 1 2 3 4 5
- Not satisfied at all Very satisfied

Future prospects and challenges

- 21. Do you feel that you have the basic knowledge of how to interact with researchers or be involved in research projects?**
Please check yes or no.
- Yes
 - No

- 21. b) If yes to the previous question, please specify.**

- 22. What are (or would be) your expectations when you are involved in polar research projects?**
Please indicate your thoughts in the box below.

- 23. Would you like to be more involved in Polar research projects?**
Please check yes or no.
- Yes
 - No

- 23. b) If yes to the previous question, please indicate in which capacity.**
- Research design
 - Outreach activities
 - Field work
 - Other: _____

- 23. c) In order to involve polar researchers in your research or to be yourself involved in polar research, what would you need?**
- More contacts and opportunities to network
 - More ideas and inspiration
 - More time
 - Financial resources
 - More knowledge of traditional/indigenous knowledge and culture
 - Other: _____

- 24. How would like the results from polar researchers to be presented to you when you work together?**
Please indicate your thoughts in the box below.

- 25. How does working with polar researchers benefit your local society?**
- Provide a better understanding of local environment
 - Provide a better understanding of local history
 - Provide better field safety
 - Avoid conflicts with local people
 - Increase outreach
 - Other: _____

- 26. What challenges do you see when researchers work in indigenous areas?**
- Lack of communication/interaction
 - Cultural differences
 - Language differences/barriers
 - Lack of interest
 - Lack of time
 - Different analytical thinking & methodologies (e.g. concept of ecosystems)
 - Other: _____

- 27. Based on your observations and experience, what elements would contribute to establish fruitful cooperation work between polar ECRs and indigenous youth?**
Please indicate your thoughts in the box below.

- 28. Other comments (on entire survey)**

- 29. Would you like to receive information about the results and outcomes of this study.**
If so please provide your email address in the box below.